

**Balancing Gene Transfection and Cytotoxicity of Nucleic Acid
Carriers with Focus on Ocular and Hepatic Disorders: Evaluation of
Hydrophobic and Hydrophilic Polyethyleneimine Derivatives**

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ABSTRACT

Polyethyleneimine (PEI) derivatives substituted by lactose, succinic acid or alkyl domains were evaluated as nonviral gene delivery vectors towards balancing gene transfection and cytotoxicity. The investigations were focused on pDNA transfection into arising retinal pigment epithelia (ARPE-19) and human hepatocellular carcinoma (HepG2) cell lines. The first mentioned cell line was chosen as motivated by the non-negligible number of ocular disorders linked to gene aberrations, whereas the second one is a cell line overexpressing the asialoglycoprotein receptor (ASGP-R), which can bind to galactose residues. The presence of short alkyl domains (C₄ and C₆), and particularly the succinylation of the PEI chains, improved the biological outputs of the gene vectors. The presence of hydrophobic units possibly enhances lytic activity, whereas the incorporation of succinic acid slightly reduces polymer-DNA interaction strength, thereby enabling more efficient intracellular unpacking and cargo release. The succinylation is also supposed to decrease cytotoxicity and avoid protein adsorption to the polyplexes. The presence of long carbon chains (for instance, C₁₂) nevertheless, results in higher levels of cytotoxicity and respective lower transfection rates. The sugar-decorated polyplexes are overall less cytotoxic, but the presence of lactose moieties also leads to larger polyplexes and notably weak polymer-DNA binding, which compromise the transfection efficiency. Yet, along with the presence of short lytic alkyl domains, the double-substitution of PEI synergistically boost gene transfection probably due to the uptake of higher DNA and polymer amounts without cell damage. Overall, the experimental data suggest that ocular and hepatic gene therapies may be potentialized by fine-tuning the hydrophobic-to-hydrophilic balance, and succinic acid is a favorable motif for the modification of PEI.

Keywords: polyethyleneimine, non-viral gene delivery, cytotoxicity, hydrophobic modification, sugar-functionalization, succinylation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Gene therapy is an encouraging strategy towards the treatment of diseases caused by genetic disorders.[1–3] This approach intends to modulate gene expression and therefore, the active agent is a nucleic acid with direct effect on these cellular processes. In this framework, the delivery of naked nucleic acids is inefficient since they are negatively charged biomacromolecules with poor permeability through the also negatively charged plasma membranes.[4] Accordingly, cargo-delivery platforms able to provide efficient cellular uptake and therapeutic activity of the biomacromolecules in the intracellular environment are required.

Viral vectors were previously demonstrated to be highly efficient in this regard,[5,6] although their use is linked to noteworthy drawbacks (undesirable interaction with the immune system and high production costs are surely some of the most relevant).[7–9] These concerns motivated the search for non-viral gene carriers and those based on polymeric materials emerged as potential candidates since the preparation is fairly simple, they are rather stable and can be designed to be relatively safe.[10–13] The polycation polyethylenimine (PEI) is one of the most extensively researched polymeric gene vectors.[14] However, the transfection efficiency still does not compete with that of viral vectors,[15] and it also exhibits significant cytotoxicity due to its membrane disruptive properties,[16,17] thus optimizations and improved derivatives are required. Furthermore, the different steps of the cellular delivery pathway generally require conflicting properties (such as extracellular stability to maintain nucleic acid complexation, but intracellular lability to release the therapeutic cargo),[18–20] which

makes challenge to find a balance between cytotoxicity and transfection performance. All these hitches can explain to some extent the limited number of non-viral formulations that have hitherto progressed to clinical trials.

Hence, strategies to enhance the effectiveness of PEI as a polymeric gene delivery vector is still a field of active research. PEI chains are easily substituted by using relatively simple synthetic approaches, thus permitting the chemical conjugation of a variety of different functional groups. This feature encouraged the manufacturing of a wide array of derivatives. In this regard, the derivatization with hydrophobic units may potentialize favorable intermolecular interactions of polymer-DNA complexes with lipid membranes, thereby leading to enhanced cellular uptake and transfection levels.[21] In addition, hydrophobic modifications can also influence the polymer-nucleic acid binding strength and complex stability.[22,23] In contrast to the unspecific membrane interactions of hydrophobic domains, decoration of polyplexes with specific sugar molecules may enhance cellular uptake *via* receptor recognition, depending on the cell type and expression characteristics. For instance, hepatocytes and hepatomas overexpress the asialoglycoprotein receptor (ASGP-R) which binds galactose and can therefore be targeted by surfaces functionalized with galactose and lactose (containing glucose and galactose residues).[24,25] This has been also evidenced by us for gold nanoparticles stabilized with lactose-containing PEI chains.[26] Furthermore, the introduction of other hydrophilic units in the PEI chains may optimize relevant parameters for efficient transfection such as the hydrophilic-lipophilic balance, the charge density, and the buffering capacity.[27]

Concerning the diseases that can be treated *via* gene therapies, it is nowadays well accepted that a non-negligible number of ocular disorders (retinitis pigmentosa, Stargardt disease and Leber congenital amaurosis to name a few) are linked to gene

aberrations.[28–30] Accordingly, gene therapy is identified as a favourable strategy since it can provide a causal treatment and the eye is accessible by local injections. Additionally, since it is also well shielded from the systemic circulation, potential unwanted side-effects in non-target tissues are unlikely. Despite intravitreal or subretinal injections, drug delivery to the posterior segments of the eye *via* anterior administration is very challenging due to several ocular barriers such as rapid drainage, tear fluid turnover, blinking and corneal epithelium cell barriers.[31] Thus, the development of optimized therapeutics for ocular diseases deserves further investigations and searching for materials with optimized properties is required. Moreover, a high number of known hereditary and metabolic diseases is originated from the liver. Here, polyplexes bearing galactose residues may improve the transfection efficiency in hepatocytes which express a galactose specific membrane lectin.[25] In such a case, cell-specific interaction and receptor-mediated endocytosis are hypothesized since galactosyl ligands in the transfecting particles may be recognized by receptors at the surface of the cells.

Taking into account all the above-mentioned considerations, we herein investigated the potential of alkyl- and lactose-modified, as well as succinylated PEI as pDNA carriers for transgene delivery to retinal and hepatic cells. The biological investigations were accordingly based on arising retinal pigment epithelia (ARPE-19) and human hepatocellular carcinoma (HepG2) human cells. The aim of the study was to confirm that the presence of alkyl domains can increase cellular uptake levels due to favorable interactions with cell membranes,[32] whereas succinylation decreases cytotoxicity, changes the internal structure of the complexes and avoids protein adsorption, leading to enhanced transfection efficiency.[33] Similarly, sugar modification of PEI was hypothesized to lead to a lower density of positive charges on the PEI complex surface, thereby reducing the overall cell cytotoxicity.[34]

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials and Chemicals

Linear polyethyleneimine (LPEI, $M_w = 25$ kDa) was purchased from Polymer Science Inc. Branched polyethyleneimine (BPEI, $M_w = 25$ kDa and 1.3 kDa), lactose monohydrate (Lac), 1-bromobutane, 1-bromohexane, 1-bromooctane and 1-bromododecane, Succinic acid, sodium borate, potassium carbonate, pyridine borane complex, *tert*-butyl alcohol and calf thymus DNA (ctDNA) were all purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. SYBR[®] Safe Green dye was purchased from Life Technologies. The plasmid pEGFP-N1 (Clontech Laboratories, USA) containing the early promoter of HCMV and the enhanced green fluorescent protein (GFP) gene was amplified in competent *Escherichia coli* and purified by using a PureLink[™] HiPure Plasmid Maxiprep (Invitrogen[™], USA) kit. The purity of the DNA was confirmed by UV absorbance at 260/280 nm. All the samples were prepared using ultrapure MilliQ[®] water.

2.2. Synthesis of the Polycations

The alkylated PEI chains were synthesized as previously described.[35] Briefly, to produce BPEI-C_n (n = 4, 6, 8 and 12), 1-bromoalkane (12 mmol) was added dropwise to a stirred BPEI solution (120 mmol per monomer) in 60 mL of *tert*-butyl alcohol containing an excess of potassium carbonate. The reaction mixture was stirred at 40 °C for 5 days and subsequently dialyzed (Spectra/Por[®] 6, MWCO = 3,500 g mol⁻¹) against distilled water for 3 days, and further lyophilized. The sugar-containing PEI derivatives were also produced using a synthetic approach reported in the literature.[36] LPEI, BPEI-1.3kDa, BPEI or BPEI-C_n (7.0 mmol per monomer) were dissolved in 30 mL of sodium borate solution (0.10 mol L⁻¹) and left for 24 hs. Lactose monohydrate (3.5 mmol) was dissolved in sodium borate solution and added to the polymer solutions. After 1 h, the

borane pyridine complex (5.0 mmol) was further added. The reaction mixtures were stirred at 50°C for 7 days and subsequently dialyzed (Spectra/Por® 6, MWCO = 3,500 g mol⁻¹, and MWCO = 1,000 g mol⁻¹ for BPEI-1.3kDa) against distilled water for 3 days and lyophilized. Succinylated PEI (BPEI-Succ) was synthesized as previously described [37]. The PEI derivatives were all characterized by proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). The molecular structures of all investigated polycations are given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Chemical structure of LPEI (A), LPEI-Lac (B), BPEI (C), BPEI-R (D), BPEI-Lac (E), BPEI-R-Lac (F) and BPEI-Succ (G). L - linear; B - branched; R - n-butyl, n-hexyl, n-octyl, n-dodecyl.

2.3. Preparation of the Electrostatic Complexes

Calf thymus DNA (ctDNA) was used to investigate structural features of the assemblies and the DNA binding properties, whereas pEGFP-N1 and pCAGGS-Luc were employed in the biological assays. Stock solutions were prepared in Hepes Buffer 25 mmol.L⁻¹ (pH 7.4). DNA was labeled by using the intercalating dye SYBR[®] Safe Green dye for fluorescence spectroscopy measurements. The ctDNA or pEGFP-N1 solutions were added to determined amounts of polymer solutions in the same buffer to obtain polyplexes at different N/P ratios. The N/P ratio is expressed as the molar ratio of amine groups (from the polymers) to phosphate groups (from DNA).

2.4. Characterization of the Polyplexes

Agarose Gel Electrophoresis: The electrophoretic mobility of polymer/DNA polyplexes as a function of the nitrogen-to-phosphate (N/P) ratio was probed by agarose gel electrophoresis. After 60 min of incubation, 2 μL of polyplex solutions containing 100 ng of ctDNA were mixed with 10 μL of loading dye and loaded into 1% agarose gel containing 3 μL of SYBR[®] Safe Green dye in TBE buffer. The electrophoresis was carried out at 100 V for 70 min and the ctDNA was visualized under UV (254 nm) illumination. 1 kb DNA ladder (Thermo Scientific, MA, USA) was used as DNA size marker.

Fluorescence Spectroscopy: The polymer/DNA complexes were produced at defined N/P ratios by mixing stock solutions of the polymers and ctDNA. Afterwards, an equivolume of SYBR[®] Safe Green dye was added to the samples. The relative fluorescence emitted by the fluorescent dye intercalated with ctDNA was measured using a microplate reader. The exclusion of the dye from the DNA leads to a reduction in

fluorescence intensity pointing out the ability of the polycations to compact the nucleic acid. The reported values of fluorescence intensity were normalized by taking into account the monitored values for DNA and SYBR[®] Safe Green dye in the absence of the polycations. The selected excitation and emission wavelengths were 480 and 520 nm, respectively. All the measurements were performed in triplicate.

Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS): The DLS measurements were performed using an ALV/CGS-3 platform-based goniometer system (ALV GmbH). The autocorrelation functions were collected using the ALV Correlator Control software. The counting time was 120 s and the distributions of sizes were obtained *via* the straightforward CONTIN analysis with reported average hydrodynamic radii (R_H) calculated using the Stokes-Einstein relation with $D = \tau^{-1}q^{-2}$:

$$R_H = \frac{k_B T q^2}{6\pi\eta} \tau \quad (1)$$

k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature, q is the scattering vector, η is the viscosity of the solvent and τ is the mean relaxation time related to the diffusion of the electrostatic complexes.

Electrophoretic Light Scattering (ELS): The measurements were used to compute the surface charge of the electrostatic complexes produced at different N/P ratios. Values of electrophoretic mobility (U_E) were collected using a Zetasizer Nano-ZS ZEN3600 instrument (Malvern Instruments, UK) and further converted to values of zeta potential (ζ) through the Henry's equation:

$$U_E = \frac{2 \varepsilon \zeta f(ka)}{3 \eta} \quad (2)$$

where ε is the dielectric constant of the medium, η its viscosity, and $f(ka)$ is the Henry's function calculated through the Smoluchowski approximation $f(ka) = 1.5$.

2.5. Biological Assays

Cell Culture: Arising retinal pigment epithelia (ARPE-19) and human hepatocellular carcinoma (HepG2) cell lines were cultured in DMEM/F12+GlutaMAX (Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium/Nutrient Mixture F-12) and DMEM (Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium) respectively, supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum and antibiotic solutions (penicillin 10,000 Units.mL⁻¹ and streptomycin 10,000 μ g.mL⁻¹) at 37°C and CO₂ atmosphere.

Cell Viability: The cytotoxicity of the polyplexes was evaluated in both cell lines (ARPE-19 and HepG2). The cells were seeded into 96-well plates at a density of 20000 cells/well, grown for 24 hs and afterwards treated with 200 μ L of fresh DMEM containing polyplexes prepared with 0.5 μ g (10 μ L polyplex solutions into 190 μ L of DMEM) of ctDNA at different N/P ratios. The cells were incubated for 24 hs at 37 °C, washed with PBS and subjected to MTT assay. One hundred- μ L of MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2yl)-2,5-diphenyl-tetrazolium bromide) reagent solution (0.3 mg mL⁻¹) was added to each well and left for 4 hs. The medium was aspirated and violet crystals of formazan generated by living cells at each well were dissolved in 100 μ L of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). The absorbance was then read at 570 nm using a Synergy microplate reader. The relative cell

viability (%) was determined by comparing the absorbance at 570 nm with control wells containing untreated cells (100%).

Luciferase Expression Assay: The luciferase assay kit for gene transfection (Promega Co.) containing the luciferase encoding gene pCAGGS-Luc was used to quantitatively evaluate the transfection rates. ARPE-19 and HepG2 cells (20000/well) were grown for 24 hs in 96-well plates, then the cell culture medium was replaced by 200 μ L of fresh DMEM containing polyplexes with 0.5 μ g (10 μ L polyplex solutions into 190 μ L of DMEM) of the plasmid pCAGGS-Luc followed by incubation for 48 hs. Afterwards, the medium was removed and the cells were lysed in 40 μ L of lysis buffer. Subsequently, 100 μ L of the luciferase assay reagent (E4550) was added to each well and the luminescence was measured in a luminometer plate reader. The total amounts of cellular protein were determined using a Micro BCATM (Pierce, Rockford, IL) protein assay kit. The values of transfection efficiency are reported as relative light units per mg of protein (RLU/mg protein).

Fluorescence Microscopy: The gene transfection was additionally evaluated qualitatively by fluorescence microscopy. The ARPE-19 and HepG2 cells were seeded into 96-well plates at a density of 20000 cells/well in the cell culture medium and incubated at 37 °C in CO₂ atmosphere for 24 hs. Next day, the cell culture medium was replaced by 200 μ L of fresh DMEM containing polyplexes with 0.5 μ g (10 μ L polyplex solutions into 190 μ L of DMEM) of the plasmid pEGFP-N1 followed by incubation for 48 hs. The images were acquired on a widefield Leica DMI 6000 B microscope (Leica Microsystems, Germany) coupled to an ultrafast Leica DFC365 FX digital camera (Leica Microsystems, Germany). The L5 (ex. 460-500 nm, DC 505 nm, em. 512-542 nm) cube filters were selected for image acquisition.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Synthesis and Characterization of the PEI Derivatives

The branched and linear polyethylenimine (PEI) were chemically modified with lactose (Lac) and-or alkyl groups, or succinic acid as described in the experimental section. The hydrophobization of the PEI chains has been conducted *via* an alkylation reaction using 1-bromododecane to produce BPEI-C₁₂. The shorter chains were similarly synthesized using respective 1-bromoalkanes. The alkylation of PEI with alkyl halides is a practical strategy to introduce hydrophobic groups into the polymeric structure *via* a bimolecular nucleophilic substitution (S_N2) reaction. The reductive amination of BPEI or BPEI-C_n with lactose leads to the formation of sugar-functionalized chains. The BPEI-Succ chains was obtained by the acetylation of the primary amines leading to amides. The BPEI and produced derivatives were characterized by ¹H NMR and representative data are portrayed in the Supporting Information File (Figures S1-S5). The ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) spectrum of BPEI shows the presence of the characteristic –CH₂CH₂N– groups at δ 2.2–3.0 ppm. The presence of the alkyl chains in BPEI-C₁₂ (400 MHz, CDCl₃) is confirmed by the signals related to the dodecyl groups linked to the amino groups: δ 0.87 ppm (H₃C(CH₂)₉CH₂CH₂NH–), δ 1.26 ppm (H₃C(CH₂)₉CH₂CH₂NH–), δ 2.2–3.2 ppm (H₃C(CH₂)₉CH₂CH₂NH–, –NH(CH₂)₂NH–), and the appearance of a new signal at δ 4.17 due to the presence of the alkylated NH groups. In the ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) spectrum of BPEI-Lac, the lactose substitution is evidenced by the signals assigned to –NH(CH₂)₂NH– at δ 2.1–3.1 ppm (with the proton from the reduced glycosidic unit), the lactose protons (except the anomeric ones) at δ 3.2–4.2 ppm and the anomeric proton of the glycosidic unit at δ 4.2–4.5 ppm. In the ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O) spectrum of BPEI-C₁₂-Lac, it is evidenced the characteristic signals at δ 0.87–1.26 ppm assigned to the protons of alkyl groups, at δ 2.2–3.2 ppm assigned to protons of BPEI and δ 3.2–4.5 ppm

assigned to protons of lactose groups. The degrees of alkyl and lactose substitution were estimated by integrating the peak areas corresponding to PEI ($-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}-$), methyl groups ($-\text{CH}_3$) of the alkyl moieties and the anomeric proton of the glycosidic unit (lactose). The ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) spectrum of BPEI-Succ shows the presence of the characteristic $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}-$ groups at δ 2.6–3.0 ppm of BPEI and methylene of succinate ($-\text{CH}_2-$) in δ 3.0–3.4 ppm. The degree of substitution was analyzed by the ratio between these peak areas. The determined degrees of substitution are all provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Degrees of substitution of the synthesized PEI derivatives as revealed by ^1H NMR.

Entry	% Alkyl substitution	% Lactose substitution	% Succinic substitution
LPEI	-	-	-
LPEI-Lac	-	15	-
BPEI-1.3kDa	-	-	-
BPEI-1.3kDa-Lac	-	14	-
BPEI	-	-	-
BPEI-Lac	-	15	-
BPEI-C ₄	9.2	-	-
BPEI-C ₄ -Lac	9.2	13	-
BPEI-C ₆	9.2	-	-
BPEI-C ₆ -Lac	9.2	13	-
BPEI-C ₈	9.1	-	-
BPEI-C ₈ -Lac	9.1	13	-
BPEI-C ₁₂	10	-	-
BPEI-C ₁₂ -Lac	10	13	-
BPEI-Succ	-	-	10

Additionally, the FTIR spectra reported in Figure S6 (Supporting Information File) evidence characteristic C–O stretching of lactose at 1066 cm^{-1} , confirming the respective chemical modification in BPEI-Lac and BPEI-C₁₂-Lac. The FTIR spectrum of BPEI-Succ shows absorption bands at 1625 cm^{-1} region assigned to the carbonyl group (C=O stretching vibration).

3.2. Manufacturing and Characterization of the Electrostatic Complexes

The electrostatic complexation between DNA and the polymer chains was induced by mixing stock aqueous solutions of ctDNA to predetermined amounts of PEI chains and respective derivatives to obtain polyplexes at different N/P ratios, which are expressed as the molar ratio of amine groups (from the polymers) to phosphate groups (from DNA). The N/P ratios were calculated based on the polymer repeating units (for instance, BPEI subunit of 43.0 g mol^{-1} - corresponding to each repeating unit of BPEI containing one amine, and a DNA subunit of 330.0 g.mol^{-1} - corresponding to the average mass of desoxynucleoside-monophosphates). As for the PEI derivatives, the polyplexes were manufactured by taking into account the respective polymer repeating units containing the substituents and the degrees of substitution determined by ¹H NMR and reported in Table 1.

The polymer-DNA binding has been initially evaluated semi-quantitatively by agarose gel electrophoresis, and the experimental data are provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Agarose gel electrophoresis of PEI-based polyplexes at different N/P ratios as specified by the labels.

In Figure 2, the first lanes refer to free ctDNA (absence of complexing agents), whereas the other ones contained increasing amounts of the polymeric materials (different N/P ratios). The DNA compaction promoted by the unsubstituted polymers (BPEI, BPEI-1.3kDa and LPEI), by the ones substituted with hydrophobic moieties (BPEI-C₄, BPEI-

C₆, BPEI-C₈, BPEI-C₁₂) or by succinylated chains (BPEI-Succ) is evidenced at N/P ~ 2-3. Conversely, the double substituted chains (BPEI-C₄-Lac, BPEI-C₆-Lac, BPEI-C₈-Lac and BPEI-C₁₂-Lac) compact the biomacromolecule to a lesser extent, thus requiring higher polymer amounts to condense the biomacromolecule. The lowest ability for DNA compaction seems to be promoted by the BPEI-C₁₂-Lac chains. Accordingly, the double substitution conducts to a notably distinct behavior since the substitution by using only alkyl chains promote high degrees of compaction. Truly, the DNA condensation seems to be mostly influenced by the presence of lactose residues as can be observed by taking into account the polyplexes produced using LPEI-Lac, BPEI-1.3kDa-Lac and BPEI-Lac. These derivatives promote a lesser degree of compaction as compared to the chains substituted by using only alkyl domains. The substitution of the polymer chains likely conducts to greater exclusion volumes and steric hindrance due to the large size, particularly of the lactose residues. This scenario possibly attenuates the strength of polymer-DNA electrostatic attraction as indeed corroborated by the overall less positive values of surface charge after total complexation at N/P = 10 (discussed hereafter). Due to the weaker binding in such cases, higher amounts of the complexing agents are required for full DNA condensation.

The capability of the basic polymers to condense DNA has been also evaluated quantitatively *via* fluorescence spectroscopy by monitoring the relative fluorescence emitted by the SYBR[®] Safe Green dye complexed to ctDNA as a function of the N/P ratio. The experimental data are provided in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Relative fluorescence intensity reduction of SYBR[®] Safe Green dye-DNA complexes in the presence of PEI-modified chains as a function of the N/P ratio as specified by the legends.

The data assigned to lactose-containing chains are provided as open symbols, whereas those for alkyl-containing and unsubstituted chains are given as filled symbols in Figure 3 as well as in Figures 4 and 5. The results are in fairly good agreement with the previously discussed agarose gel electrophoresis data. The profiles acquired for polyplexes produced by using alkyl-modified chains highlights their high capability to condense DNA since the relative fluorescence is essentially neutralized at $N/P \sim 2-3$, similar to the unsubstituted polymers. On the other hand, lactose-containing PEI derivatives compact the biomacromolecule to a notably lesser extent, regardless of the molecular weight of the polycation. Consistently, the compaction ability of the double modified chains is also notably weak. The data again underscore that the degree of compaction seems to be mainly governed by the presence of lactose with minor influence

The acquired data also suggest DNA compaction and the neutralization of the negative charges of the biomacromolecule as the polymer concentration increases. The obvious presence of free DNA is confirmed by the negative charges monitored at $N/P = 0$, and in general for $N/P < 1$. When the polymer concentration (N/P) increases, the ζ -potential passes values close to ~ 0 mV and afterwards, positive values were monitored meaning, accordingly, excess of polymer chains neutralizing the nucleic acids. Overall, the unsubstituted chains compact DNA at lower N/P ratios and regardless of the architecture or molecular weight, the introduction of lactose residues reduces the degree of compaction. This is indeed in full agreement with the previously reported agarose gel electrophoresis and fluorescence spectroscopy data. The same trend is evidenced for the succinylated derivative (BPEI-Succ) although, this type of modification attenuates the continuous increase of surface charge with increasing N/P to a much lower extent. On the other hand, the introduction of alkyl moieties does not remarkably change the zeta potential *vs.* N/P feature, therefore suggesting that the degree of compaction is independent on the presence of such type of residue. The assemblies produced using double functionalized chains require higher amounts of the complexing agents to neutralize the negatively charged phosphate groups, thus underscoring once again a weaker complexing capability. The degree of compaction provided by LPEI-Lac is also notably weak whereas the molecular weight does not change remarkably the ζ -potential *vs.* N/P ratio profiles. Comparing the PEI chains containing alkyl residues, only those containing also lactose have attenuated degree of DNA compaction. Overall, the whole set of data concerning the structural characterization of the polyplexes highlight the notably weaker capability of the sugar-containing polymer chains to compact DNA, particularly those also substituted with alkyl domains. This feature has an important impact in the gene delivery performance as discussed hereafter.

Subsequently, the size of the polymeric assemblies *vs.* N/P ratio was probed by dynamic light scattering and representative experimental trends are provided in Figure 5 (A) along with the whole set of sizes at N/P = 10 (B).

Figure 5. Trends of particle size *vs.* N/P ratio during DNA complexation for polyplexes produced using different PEI-derivatives as specified by the legends (A). Values of hydrodynamic radius (R_H) for a variety of polymer/DNA polyplexes at N/P = 10 according to the labels (B).

The data reported in Figure 5A reveals interesting trends of particle size *vs.* N/P ratio. The size of the complexes produced by using unsubstituted and alkyl-substituted PEI (representatively illustrated for BPEI-C₆) evidences a notable size increase at N/P ~ 1-2 for branched chains and at N/P ~ 3-4 for the linear architecture. These values of N/P

ratio are in the range where the ζ -potential of the assemblies are close to 0 mV. In this region, the formation of relatively unstable coacervates is supposed to take place, and they are further dissolved when increasing amounts of PEI are added due to the excess of positive charges in the systems, thereby reducing the overall size of the assemblies. The trends reported in Figure 5A underscore once again that the compaction achieved by the linear polymer is weaker than the compaction provided by the branched chains. Interestingly, the formation of large coacervates seems not to take place during DNA complexation using lactose-containing and BPEI-Succ chains. Possibly, the hydrated residues provide sufficient steric stabilization, although the particle charge is close to zero (ζ -potential \sim 0 mV). In the range of N/P ratios where excess of positive charges is present, a notable reduction in particle size is noticed for polyplexes produced using lactose-free chains. Once again in agreement with the previously reported data, the DNA condensation seems to be less efficient by using BPEI-C₄-Lac, BPEI-C₆-Lac, BPEI-C₈-Lac and BPEI-C₁₂-Lac. This is suggested by the less pronounced reduction in the size of the assemblies as a function of the N/P ratio, and by the values of particle size at N/P = 10 provided in Figure 5B. The sizes of the sugar-containing polyplexes are larger than the counterparts and accordingly, all set of experimental data robustly confirm that the sugar residues conduct to a compaction of the DNA chains to a lesser extent.

3.3. Biological Assays

Evaluation of Cell Cytotoxicity: The MTT assay was used to probe the cytotoxicity of the polymer-DNA electrostatic complexes in contact with HepG2 and ARPE-19 cells. The cell lines were selected based on the scope of the investigation focused on the potential treatment of hepatic and ocular diseases. Additionally, they are also chosen since one of them regards to a healthy (ARPE-19) and the other one to a cancer (HepG2) cell

line, therefore notably different with respect to morphology and metabolism. Taking into account the previously determined N/P range where polymer-DNA complexation occurred, respectively the neutralization of the phosphate groups of the biomacromolecule by the polycations, the investigations were also performed at higher values since the polymer amount (bound or free) was previously evidenced to lead to relevant biological consequences.[38,39] Accordingly, the experiments were performed at N/P ratios of 5, 10, 15 and 30. The ctDNA amount was a fixed parameter (0.5 µg) whereas the polymer concentration was variable depending on the N/P ratio. Indeed, concerning *in vivo* applications, the delivered number of DNA copies is particularly relevant. For instance, the number of copies to be delivered in large mammals is expected to be in the range of 10^{13} copies/kg,[40] thus corresponding to roughly 2×10^{-11} mol/kg or 100 µg/kg of 10 kb pDNA. Nevertheless, these numbers have to be considered only as rough estimations since they depend on many variables, including the size of the plasmid. Indeed, the use of non-viral vectors is a clever strategy in this regard since it can carry more than one DNA copy, which is the loading capacity of a viral vector (one copy *per* capsid).

The cytotoxicity of the polyplexes was evaluated by placing the cells in contact with the produced supramolecular assemblies, and the cell viability was determined in comparison with control wells containing untreated cells. Since a relatively high number of samples was investigated, the results were split into three figures for the benefit of readers. In Figures 6A and 6D it is given the results for polyplexes produced using alkyl-modified and succinylated chains, the results concerning chains modified by sugar moieties are given in Figures 6B and 6E, and the polyplexes produced using double-modified chains are provided in Figures 6C and 6F, respectively for HepG2 and ARPE-

19 cells according to the labels, and along with unsubstituted chains for comparison purposes.

Figure 6. Viability of HepG2 and ARPE-19 cells in contact for 24 hs with polyplexes produced at different N/P ratios according to legends (results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation of 3 independent experiments).

The polyplexes produced using alkyl-modified chains are overall slightly more cytotoxic as N/P ratio increases, particularly when they are in contact with ARPE-19 cells. This means that the cytotoxicity is dependent on the polymer concentration, and the cell viability is reduced when relatively high polymer amounts are present. The longer alkyl chains (particularly C₈ and C₁₂) reduce the viability of ARPE-19 cells more pronounced. Nevertheless, according to the ISO 10993-5:2009, which considers a cytotoxic effect the reduction in cell viability by more than 30% compared to the control (respectively, cell viability below 70%), in contact with HepG2 cells, the electrostatic complexes are overall low cytotoxic (> 70% cell viability) even at N/P = 30. Values below 70% were only found for polyplexes produced using BPEI-C₁₂ at N/P ≥ 10 and for those produced using BPEI-C₈ at N/P ≥ 15 in contact with ARPE-19 cells.

As for the sugar-containing polyplexes, up to N/P = 30 the values of cell viability are still above 70%. Interestingly, values of cell viability always above 70% were also monitored for polyplexes produced using the double-substituted chains, thus suggesting that in the presence of the sugar moieties, the toxicity occasioned by the alkyl chains is attenuated. This can be evidenced for instance comparing BPEI-C₈ and BPEI-C₈-Lac or BPEI-C₁₂ and BPEI-C₁₂-Lac at a given N/P ratio. The viability of the cells in contact with polyplexes produced using BPEI-C₈-Lac and BPEI-C₁₂-Lac were monitored to be always above 70% regardless of the N/P ratio, which is not the case of the counterparts at N/P ≥ 15. The succinylation (BPEI-Succ) also does not conduct to higher levels of cytotoxicity as compared to the unsubstituted chains.

Taking into account the different cell lines, HepG2 seems to be slightly more resistant than ARPE-19 since the values of cell viability monitored is generally higher for the first case. This is presumably linked to the structural and metabolic differences of the living systems. The HepG2 is a cancer cell line which to some extent justify the greater

resistance. The ARPE-19 cells come from the retinal pigment epithelium and therefore, it is supposed to be more sensitive to external agents.

Evaluation of Cell Transfection: The investigations concerning the *in-vitro* luciferase gene expression were similarly performed by treating the HepG2 and ARPE-19 cells with all the polyplexes at N/P ratios of 5, 10, 15 and 30. The results are also split into three figures. In Figures 7A and B it is given the results for polyplexes produced using alkyl-modified and succinylated chains, the results concerning chains modified by sugar moieties are given in Figures 7B and 7E, and the polyplexes produced using double-modified chains are portrayed in Figures 7C and 7F, respectively for HepG2 and ARPE-19 cells according to the labels, and along with unsubstituted chains for comparison purposes. The experiments were performed by using pCAGGS-Luc plasmid as reporter gene. The transfection efficiency increases with the N/P ratio as expected to some extent. This is linked to enhanced DNA protection caused by the thicker copolymer layers nevertheless, this is also attributed to the presence of free (uncomplexed) chains as evidenced by us [41] and by others[42] to be required in order to notably enhance gene transfection. Additionally, the values clearly depend on the chemical nature of the complexing agent and respectively, on the chemical modifications performed in the polycations.

Figure 7. *In-vitro* luciferase expression in HepG2 and ARPE-19 cells after 48 hs incubation time as mediated by different polycations at various N/P ratios according to the legend.

The control BPEI chains are evidenced to be notably effective as a transfecting agent for HepG2 cells nevertheless, the transfection efficiency reduces by increasing N/P ratio for ARPE-19 cells thus pointing out higher susceptibility of this cell line to the presence of polycations. The linear configuration seems to be a better transfecting agent for ARPE-19 cells. Although fairly low values of luciferase expression were in general monitored at lower N/P ratios, a notable increase has been evidenced for N/P ratios of 15 and 30 in many cases. The influence of the molecular weight can be clearly seen by comparing BPEI (25 kDa) with BPEI-1.3kDa. Regardless of the cell line, higher transfection efficiency has been monitored for the longer chains as similarly reported for polycation of disparate chemical nature.[43] Importantly, the experimental data reported in Figure 7 underline that at high N/P ratio the short alky chains (C₄-C₆) enhance the transfection efficiency in ARPE-19 cells as compared to the unsubstituted counterpart (BPEI). For instance, at N/P = 30 the transfection efficiency provided by BPEI-C₆ is about 10-fold higher. Nevertheless, they are not more effective than BPEI in transfecting HepG2 cells, and the complex agents BPEI-C₈ and BPEI-C₁₂ have a marked attenuated ability to transfect both cell lines as most probably linked to cytotoxic effects. The branched PEI chains containing lactose are slightly more effective to transfect ARPE-19 cells, however only at the highest N/P ratio. Since the DNA binding strength is markedly weak for lactose-containing chains as discussed previously, and this is expected to decrease the transfection rates, the reported behavior is probably justified by the reduced cytotoxicity of the sugar-modified chains which allows for higher amounts of cellular uptake without causing relevant cell damage. Nevertheless, overall the presence of lactose domains decreases transfection rates, regardless of the polymer architecture, meaning that the phenomenon is mainly driven by the weakening of the polymer-DNA binding

strength. Yet, cell line-dependent feature is possibly linked to structural and metabolic differences of the living systems.

The double-substituted chains are also effective to transfect ARPE-19 cells at the highest N/P ratio nevertheless, the complexing agents produced with the polymer chains containing a relatively long alkyl domain (C₁₂) demonstrated remarkably attenuated performance. The reduced transfection efficiency evidenced is possibly linked to a combination of enhanced cytotoxicity due to the presence of the long carbon domain, and the reduced polymer-DNA binding affinity. Indeed, the polyplexes produced using the longer alkyl chains demonstrated highest values of gene expression at N/P = 10-15, thus suggesting relevant degrees of cytotoxicity as N/P increases. This trend is not evidenced for sugar-containing chains and such behavior once again underlines the attenuated cytotoxicity of this type of vector and higher degrees of cytotoxicity essentially linked to the presence of the longer hydrocarbon chains. Furthermore, the structural characterization of the polyplexes underscored that, due to the large volume, particularly of the chains containing both, sugar and alkyl residues, the electrostatic complexes are notably larger therefore presumably also hampering to some extent the cellular uptake, which is known to be size-dependent[44] and respectively, the transfection efficiency. Yet, although the presence of short alkyl chains along with lactose units reduces the DNA binding strength, in such cases, an optimized combination of lytic activity and reduced cell damage is supposed to provide enhanced transfection rates at high N/P ratios as compared to unsubstituted chains, at least in ARPE-19 cells.

Most important, amongst all evaluated polycations, outstanding performance has been monitored for BPEI-Succ. The transfection efficiency provide by the BPEI-Succ chains is notably higher than the monitored values for BPEI (about 16-fold and 40-fold higher respectively for HepG2 and ARPE-19 cells at N/P = 30). Indeed, the values of

luciferase expression are notably higher than those monitored for any other system for HepG2, and similar efficiencies are reported for BPEI-Succ and LPEI with regard to ARPE-19 cells. Besides greater transfection efficiency, the behavior is also associated to relatively low levels of cell toxicity, even for the highest N/P ratio probed (N/P = 30). Depending on the degree of substitution, succinylation of PEI chains may optimize the polymer/DNA interaction strength to balance stability-lability, as well as they provide stability to the vector at the serum medium,[33] thus allowing for enhanced transfection levels.[45] This output can also be linked, at least to some extent, to lower polymer toxicity.[37] Truly, these assumptions seem not to be clear enough at this moment, and we are conducting investigations in this regard to better identify the main reason linked to the outstanding performance of the BPEI-Succ chains.

The gene expression levels were complementary qualitatively evaluated by direct visualization under fluorescence microscopy. Relevant representative data are provided in Figures 8 and Figure 9 respectively for HepG2 and ARPE-19 cell lines. The fluorescence microscopy data are in fairly good agreement with the previously reported and discussed luciferase assays. The images robustly confirm the pEGFP-N1 expression and suggest the most promising candidates for gene transfection. Importantly, the images demonstrate homogenous transfection, therefore confirming an effective process not concentrated only in a few number of cells. One can identify that the derivatization of the PEI chains by using small hydrophobic domains (C₄) conduct to a relevant level of transfection rate. The high transfection efficiency reached when the BPEI chains were modified with a short alkyl moiety implies that such derivatizations might be useful to transfect particularly hard-to-transfect cells such as ARPE-19.[46] The overall reduction in the luciferase expression as N/P increases is most probably linked to the increased toxicity to the cells. This is clearly evidenced in Figures 8 and 9 by comparing the

experimental data acquired for polyplexes produced using BPEI-C₄ and BPEI-C₈, thus in full agreement with the previously reported and discussed experimental data.

Figure 8. Bright field and fluorescence images of *in-vitro* EGFP expression in HepG2 cells mediated by different polycations at various N/P ratios after 48 hs incubation time according to the legends (all images were acquired under the same experimental conditions).

Figure 9. Bright field and fluorescence images of *in-vitro* EGFP expression in ARPE-19 cells mediated by different polycations at various N/P ratios after 48 hs incubation time according to the legends (all images were acquired under the same experimental conditions).

The luciferase expression is visually reduced and it is higher at lower values of N/P for the longer alkyl chain. Indeed, the presence of hydrophobic domains are understood to improve the stability of the polyplexes and the lytic activity, hence enhancing membrane disruptive properties and permitting smoother endosomal escape. Nevertheless, it can also induce higher degrees of cytotoxicity due to favorable interactions with biological membranes.[23,47] Accordingly, the current investigation underlines a clear length-dependent membranolytic activity and these results emphasize that an optimized level of hydrophobicity is required in order to balance lytic potential, endosomal release and cytotoxicity towards the augmentation of cell transfection rates. Additionally, the fluorescence microscopy data once again highlight the outstanding transfection efficiency promoted by the BPEI-Succ chains, regardless of the cell line. This has been suggested to be mainly linked to reduced cytotoxicity of the modified chains.[37] Nevertheless, succinylated chains may also decrease the polymer-DNA interaction strength[33] as also suggested by the herein reported experimental data. Attenuated electrostatic interactions might thus allow for a more efficient DNA unpacking in the intracellular environment, which is indeed required for efficient delivery of genetic material. The similar efficiencies reported for BPEI-Succ and LPEI particularly for ARPE-19 cells suggest that the compaction ability may be the main driven force governing the biological outputs. Truly, exceedingly strong binding might prevent the unpacking and conduct to intracellular DNA degradation. Nevertheless, notably weaker

polymer-DNA binding remarkably reduces the transfection rates such as herein evidenced for the case of double-substituted PEI chains, particularly when the longer carbon domains are present. Furthermore, the presence of the carboxyl groups in the BPEI-Succ polyplexes may also induce a hydration layer coating the assemblies, hence repelling serum proteins to a high extent. The possible presence of lower amounts of protein adsorption coating the BPEI-Succ/DNA polyplexes may enhance the cellular uptake of the assemblies as compared to the counterparts. This can be also highly relevant to explain the behavior since this scientific investigation has been performed in serum-supplemented conditions. Truly, the use of cationic polymers for gene delivery purposes is commonly limited by aggregation and reduced transfection efficacy in the presence of serum proteins. Therefore, these experimental results are supposed to be highly relevant to the field. As a vision of future work, we already have investigations underway to precisely determine the driven reasons for the outstanding behavior of the BPEI-Succ chains. We are focusing the efforts to particularly understand protein adsorption events and polymer-DNA binding strength as being probed essentially by using isothermal titration calorimetry and light scattering techniques.

CONCLUSIONS

Polyethyleneimine derivatives based on sugar, succinic acid and alkyl modifications were evaluated as nonviral gene delivery vectors towards improved gene transfection and reduced cytotoxicity. The investigations were particularly focused on arising retinal pigment epithelia (ARPE-19) cell line as motivated by the non-negligible number of ocular disorders linked to gene aberrations. HepG2 cell transfection was also probed to evaluate possible sugar receptor recognition features. Stable electrostatic complexes were produced with hydrodynamic radius ranging from 75-135 nm. The use

of sugar-containing polycations resulted in notably larger assemblies with weakened polymer-DNA binding strength. The lactose-decoration of the polyplexes does not notably improve the transfection efficiency for the investigated cell lines nevertheless, it attenuates the cytotoxicity of the assemblies. On the other hand, regardless of the cell line, the PEI derivatization using small hydrophobic domains (C₄-C₆) and particularly succinic acid notably enhances the biological outputs of the gene vectors. Furthermore, along with the presence of lytic short alkyl chains the presence of lactose (double substituted polycations) seems to synergically boost endosomal escape due to the possible uptake of higher polymer amounts without relevant cell damage. Overall, although distinct magnitudes have been monitored, relevant trends were evidenced to be cell line-independent, notably: *i*) BPEI-Succ is evidenced to be an outstanding transfecting agent for both cell lines; *ii*) the transfection efficiency is reduced when longer alkyl chains are used (C₈ and C₁₂); *iii*) lactose substitution also mostly reduces the transfection efficacy in both cell lines; *iv*) shorter polycations were evidenced to be less effective in transfecting both cell lines. Accordingly, these results highlight that ocular and hepatic gene delivery can be potentialized by using small hydrophobic moieties along with lactose domains, and principally, succinic acid linked to the PEI chains.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Fernando A. de Oliveira: Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing - Review & Editing; **Lindomar J. C. Albuquerque:** Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing - Review & Editing; **Michelle Nascimento-Sales:** Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing - Review & Editing; **Marcelo A. Christoffolete:** Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition; **Ismael C. Bellettini:** Resources,

Supervision, Writing - Review & Editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition;
Fernando C. Giacomelli: Conceptualization, Resources, Data Curation, Writing -
Original Draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST'

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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REFERENCES

- [1] L.W. Seymour, A.J. Thrasher, Gene therapy matures in the clinic, *Nat. Biotechnol.* 30 (2012) 588–593. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.2290>.
- [2] T. Wirth, N. Parker, S. Ylä-Herttuala, History of gene therapy, *Gene.* 525 (2013) 162–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gene.2013.03.137>.

- [3] F. Arabi, V. Mansouri, N. Ahmadbeigi, Gene therapy clinical trials, where do we go? An overview, *Biomed. Pharmacother.* 153 (2022) 113324. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2022.113324>.
- [4] H. Lomas, J. Du, I. Canton, J. Madsen, N. Warren, S.P. Armes, A.L. Lewis, G. Battaglia, Efficient encapsulation of plasmid DNA in pH-sensitive PMPC-PDPA polymersomes: Study of the effect of PDPA block length on copolymer-DNA binding affinity, *Macromol. Biosci.* 10 (2010) 513–530. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mabi.201000083>.
- [5] K. Lundstrom, Viral Vectors in Gene Therapy, *Diseases.* 6 (2018) 42. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diseases6020042>.
- [6] J.T. Bulcha, Y. Wang, H. Ma, P.W.L. Tai, G. Gao, Viral vector platforms within the gene therapy landscape, *Signal Transduct. Target. Ther.* 6 (2021) 53. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-021-00487-6>.
- [7] T. Hollon, Researchers and regulators reflect on first gene therapy death, *Nat. Med.* 6 (2000) 6. <https://doi.org/10.1038/71545>.
- [8] S.H. Orkin, P. Reilly, Paying for future success in gene therapy, *Science* 352 (2016) 1059–1061. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaf4770>.
- [9] C.E. Thomas, A. Ehrhardt, M.A. Kay, Progress and problems with the use of viral vectors for gene therapy, *Nat. Rev. Genet.* 4 (2003) 346–358. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrg1066>.
- [10] U. Lächelt, E. Wagner, Nucleic Acid Therapeutics Using Polyplexes: A Journey of 50 Years (and Beyond), *Chem. Rev.* 115 (2015) 11043–11078. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr5006793>.
- [11] L. Peng, E. Wagner, Polymeric Carriers for Nucleic Acid Delivery: Current Designs and Future Directions, *Biomacromolecules.* 20 (2019) 3613–3626.

- <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.9b00999>.
- [12] F.A. de Oliveira, L.J.C. Albuquerque, G. Delecourt, V. Bennevault, P. Guégan, F.C. Giacomelli, Current Designs of Polymeric Platforms Towards the Delivery of Nucleic Acids Inside the Cells with Focus on Polyethylenimine, *Curr. Gene Ther.* 21 (2021) 431–451. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1566523221666210705130238>.
- [13] P. Zhang, E. Wagner, History of Polymeric Gene Delivery Systems, *Top. Curr. Chem.* 375 (2017) 26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41061-017-0112-0>.
- [14] C. Jiang, J. Chen, Z. Li, Z. Wang, W. Zhang, J. Liu, Recent advances in the development of polyethylenimine-based gene vectors for safe and efficient gene delivery, *Expert Opin. Drug Deliv.* 16 (2019) 363–376. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17425247.2019.1604681>.
- [15] Y. Yue, C. Wu, Progress and perspectives in developing polymeric vectors for in vitro gene delivery, *Biomater. Sci.* 1 (2013) 152–170. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c2bm00030j>.
- [16] B.D. Monnery, M. Wright, R. Cavill, R. Hoogenboom, S. Shaunak, J.H.G. Steinke, M. Thanou, Cytotoxicity of polycations: Relationship of molecular weight and the hydrolytic theory of the mechanism of toxicity, *Int. J. Pharm.* 521 (2017) 249–258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2017.02.048>.
- [17] D. Fischer, Y. Li, B. Ahlemeyer, J. Krieglstein, T. Kissel, In vitro cytotoxicity testing of polycations: Influence of polymer structure on cell viability and hemolysis, *Biomaterials.* 24 (2003) 1121–1131. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-9612\(02\)00445-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-9612(02)00445-3).
- [18] B. Shi, M. Zheng, W. Tao, R. Chung, D. Jin, D. Ghaffari, O.C. Farokhzad, Challenges in DNA Delivery and Recent Advances in Multifunctional Polymeric DNA Delivery Systems, *Biomacromolecules.* 18 (2017) 2231–2246.

- <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.7b00803>.
- [19] J. Chen, K. Wang, J. Wu, H. Tian, X. Chen, Polycations for Gene Delivery: Dilemmas and Solutions, *Bioconjug. Chem.* 30 (2018) 338–349. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.bioconjchem.8b00688>.
- [20] Y.Y. Won, R. Sharma, S.F. Konieczny, Missing pieces in understanding the intracellular trafficking of polycation/DNA complexes, *J. Control. Release.* 139 (2009) 88–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2009.06.031>.
- [21] Z. Liu, Z. Zhang, C. Zhou, Y. Jiao, Hydrophobic modifications of cationic polymers for gene delivery, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* 35 (2010) 1144–1162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2010.04.007>.
- [22] N.P. Gabrielson, D.W. Pack, Acetylation of Polyethylenimine Enhances Gene Delivery via Weakened Polymer/DNA Interactions, *Biomacromolecules.* 7 (2006) 2427–2435. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bm060300u>.
- [23] S. Berger, A. Krhač Levačić, E. Hörterer, U. Wilk, T. Benli-Hoppe, Y. Wang, Ö. Öztürk, J. Luo, E. Wagner, Optimizing pDNA Lipo-polyplexes: A Balancing Act between Stability and Cargo Release, *Biomacromolecules.* 22 (2021) 1282–1296. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.0c01779>.
- [24] A. Dehshahri, H. Sadeghpour, E. Mohazzabieh, S. Saatchi Avval, R. Mohammadinejad, Targeted double domain nanoplex based on galactosylated polyethylenimine enhanced the delivery of IL-12 plasmid, *Biotechnol. Prog.* 36 (2020) 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1002/btpr.3002>.
- [25] J. Han, Y. Il Yeom, Specific gene transfer mediated by galactosylated poly-L-lysine into hepatoma cells, *Int. J. Pharm.* 202 (2000) 151–160. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5173\(00\)00441-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5173(00)00441-5).
- [26] C. A. S. Ribeiro, L. J. C. Albuquerque, C.E. de Castro, R.M. Pereira, B.L.

- Albuquerque, E. Pavlova, L. Gabriela Schlüter, B.L. Batista, I.C. Bellettini, F.C. Giacomelli, Ready-to-use room temperature one-pot synthesis of surface-decorated gold nanoparticles with targeting attributes, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 614 (2022) 489–501. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2022.01.145>.
- [27] D. He, K. Müller, A. Krhac Levačić, P. Kos, U. Lächelt, E. Wagner, Combinatorial Optimization of Sequence-Defined Oligo(ethanamino)amides for Folate Receptor-Targeted pDNA and siRNA Delivery, *Bioconjug. Chem.* 27 (2016) 647–659. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.bioconjchem.5b00649>.
- [28] P. Mastorakos, S.P. Kambhampati, M.K. Mishra, T. Wu, E. Song, J. Hanes, R.M. Kannan, Hydroxyl PAMAM dendrimer-based gene vectors for transgene delivery to human retinal pigment epithelial cells, *Nanoscale.* 7 (2015) 3845–3856. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4nr04284k>.
- [29] L. Petit, H. Khanna, C. Punzo, Advances in gene therapy for diseases of the eye, *Hum. Gene Ther.* 27 (2016) 563–579. <https://doi.org/10.1089/hum.2016.040>.
- [30] M.M. Liu, J. Tuo, C.C. Chan, Gene therapy for ocular diseases, *Br. J. Ophthalmol.* 95 (2011) 604–612. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjo.2009.174912>.
- [31] T.F. Martens, K. Remaut, H. Deschout, J.F.J. Engbersen, W.E. Hennink, M.J. Van Steenberghe, J. Demeester, S.C. De Smedt, K. Braeckmans, Coating nanocarriers with hyaluronic acid facilitates intravitreal drug delivery for retinal gene therapy, *J. Control. Release.* 202 (2015) 83–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2015.01.030>.
- [32] L.W.C. Ho, W.Y. Yung, K.H.S. Sy, H.Y. Li, C.K.K. Choi, K.C.F. Leung, T.W.Y. Lee, C.H.J. Choi, Effect of Alkylation on the Cellular Uptake of Polyethylene Glycol-Coated Gold Nanoparticles, *ACS Nano.* 11 (2017) 6085–6101. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nano.7b02044>.

- [33] L.W. Warriner, J.R. Duke, D.W. Pack, J.E. Derouchey, Succinylated Polyethylenimine Derivatives Greatly Enhance Polyplex Serum Stability and Gene Delivery in Vitro, *Biomacromolecules*. 19 (2018) 4348–4357. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.8b01248>.
- [34] L.J.C. Albuquerque, A.C. Alavarse, M.C. Carlan da Silva, M.S. Zilse, M.T. Barth, I.C. Bellettini, F.C. Giacomelli, Sweet Vector for Gene Delivery: the Sugar Decoration of Polyplexes Reduces Cytotoxicity with a Balanced Effect on Gene Expression, *Macromol. Biosci.* 18 (2018) 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mabi.201700299>.
- [35] I.C. Bellettini, L.G. Nandi, R. Eising, J.B. Domingos, V.G. Machado, E. Minatti, Properties of aqueous solutions of hydrophobically modified polyethylene imines in the absence and presence of sodium dodecylsulfate, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 370 (2012) 94–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2011.12.049>.
- [36] I.C. Bellettini, M.A. Witt, R. Borsali, E. Minatti, A.F. Rubira, E.C. Muniz, PS-b-PAA nanovesicles coated by modified PEIs bearing hydrophobic and hydrophilic groups, *J. Mol. Liq.* 210 (2015) 29–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2015.01.011>.
- [37] A. Zintchenko, A. Philipp, A. Dehshahri, E. Wagner, Simple modifications of branched PEI lead to highly efficient siRNA carriers with low toxicity, *Bioconjug. Chem.* 19 (2008) 1448–1455. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bc800065f>.
- [38] B. Chen, L. Yu, Z. Li, C. Wu, Design of Free Triblock Polylysine-b-Polyleucine-b-Polylysine Chains for Gene Delivery, *Biomacromolecules*. 19 (2018) 1347–1357. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.8b00287>.
- [39] Z. Dai, T. Gjetting, M.A. Matthebjerg, C. Wu, T.L. Andresen, Elucidating the interplay between DNA-condensing and free polycations in gene transfection

- through a mechanistic study of linear and branched PEI, *Biomaterials*. 32 (2011) 8626–8634. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2011.07.044>.
- [40] Z. Wang, T. Zhu, C. Qiao, L. Zhou, B. Wang, J. Zhang, C. Chen, J. Li, X. Xiao, Adeno-associated virus serotype 8 efficiently delivers genes to muscle and heart, *Nat. Biotechnol.* 23 (2005) 321–328. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt1073>.
- [41] L.J.C. Albuquerque, C.E. de Castro, K.A. Riske, M.C.C. Da Silva, P.I.R. Muraro, V. Schmidt, C. Giacomelli, F.C. Giacomelli, Gene Transfection Mediated by Cationic Polymers Requires Free Highly Charged Polymer Chains to Overcome Intracellular Barriers, *Biomacromolecules*. 18 (2017) 1918–1927. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.7b00344>.
- [42] J. Cai, Y. Yue, Y. Wang, Z. Jin, F. Jin, C. Wu, Quantitative study of effects of free cationic chains on gene transfection in different intracellular stages, *J. Control. Release*. 238 (2016) 71–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2016.07.031>.
- [43] J.M. Layman, S.M. Ramirez, M.D. Green, T.E. Long, Influence of polycation molecular weight on poly(2-dimethylaminoethyl methacrylate)-mediated DNA delivery in vitro, *Biomacromolecules*. 10 (2009) 1244–1252. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bm9000124>.
- [44] I. Canton, G. Battaglia, Endocytosis at the nanoscale, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 41 (2012) 2718. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c2cs15309b>.
- [45] M.R. Elzes, I. Mertens, O. Sedlacek, B. Verbraeken, A.C.A. Doensen, M.A. Mees, M. Glassner, S. Jana, J.M.J. Paulusse, R. Hoogenboom, Linear Poly(ethylenimine-propylenimine) Random Copolymers for Gene Delivery: From Polymer Synthesis to Efficient Transfection with High Serum Tolerance, *Biomacromolecules*. 23 (2022) 2459–2470. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.2c00210>.
- [46] R.B. Shmueli, J.C. Sunshine, Z. Xu, E.J. Duh, J.J. Green, Gene delivery

nanoparticles specific for human microvasculature and macrovasculature, *Nanomedicine Nanotechnology, Biol. Med.* 8 (2012) 1200–1207.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nano.2012.01.006>.

- [47] T. Fröhlich, D. Edinger, R. Kläger, C. Troiber, E. Salcher, N. Badgajar, I. Martin, D. Schaffert, A. Cengizeroglu, P. Hadwiger, H.P. Vornlocher, E. Wagner, Structure-activity relationships of siRNA carriers based on sequence-defined oligo (ethane amino) amides, *J. Control. Release.* 160 (2012) 532–541.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2012.03.018>.